

EFFECTIVE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

Ruziyeva Munisxon Komiljonovna,
an English teacher at Tashkent Academic
Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: this article provides information about how to discover the keys to harmony in your classroom. We'll explore pro tips for controlling student behavior, fostering positive relationships, managing documentation, tracking trends, and more. You'll walk away confident and equipped to create a structured learning environment where students can thrive.

Key words: classroom management, structured learning environment

As a teacher, establishing effective classroom management can be challenging. However, setting clear expectations and routines early on is key to creating a productive learning environment. Here are some useful tips:

Set the Tone from Day One

- Greet students at the door with a smile to build rapport
- Clearly communicate classroom rules, schedules, and procedures
- Be consistent in enforcing expectations to establish trust

Build Positive Relationships

- Get to know your students as individuals
- Actively listen and validate their perspectives
- Encourage peer support and collaboration

Address Challenging Behaviors Proactively

- Redirect off-task students privately
- Use positive reinforcement for good behavior

Vol. 2 No. 6 (2024)

- Involve parents to resolve recurring issues

With patience and consistency, you can implement classroom management strategies to engage students and facilitate impactful learning. Reach out for mentoring if needed - you've got this!

Classroom management can be broken down into 4 key areas known as the "Four Cs": Control

Establishing control in the classroom is vital for new teachers. This involves setting clear expectations and rules from day one. Make sure students understand what appropriate behavior looks like. Consistently reinforce these rules through positive and negative consequences.

Clarity

Ensure your lessons and assignments are clear for students. Break complex tasks down into simple steps. Check frequently for understanding. Unclear expectations are a common trigger for misbehavior.

Consistency

Be reliable in applying consequences for good and bad behavior. Don't make empty threats and follow through when rules are broken. Hold every student accountable in the same way.

Care

Get to know your students personally and build positive relationships. Make them feel valued. Show you care about their wellbeing inside and outside school. This motivates them to meet classroom expectations.

The four Cs work together to create an engaging environment where students can thrive academically and socially. Mastering these classroom management basics will lead to a productive, disruption-free space for meaningful learning.

Effective classroom management begins with strong organizational skills—preparing your materials carefully, practicing with the technology, and getting a

sense of how to best organize and move around in the room, but that's not where the planning ends. Effective classroom management is a vital skill for any teacher. We explore what it is, why it's needed and provide guidance on how you can sharpen your classroom management skills from the comfort of home. As a teacher, you need to juggle an awful lot day-to-day. In order to effectively fulfil your duties in a confident and assuring manner, being able to manage your classroom is essential. Classroom management is a critical skill and knowing exactly how it works can help to ensure success, which is why we have put together this all-you-need-to-know guide. Classroom management encompasses a variety of skills and techniques that teachers can use to create a high-performing learning environment. At its core, it aims to ensure classes run smoothly, disruptive behaviour from students is kept to a minimum, and teaching materials and activities promote learning. The ultimate goal is to ensure that both the students and the teacher get the most out of the classroom experience.

Effective classroom management is incredibly important because without it you will not be able to create a learning environment that has a positive classroom culture. Achieving effective classroom management also reduces the likelihood of suffering from work-related stress and anxiety, and you'll probably find that it leads to greater work satisfaction. Let's face it, we all want to be able to go to work every day with a smile. Not only will it encourage your students to grow, but you'll also start to perform better as a teacher, which will stand you in good stead when it comes to career progression and development. Simply put, effective classroom management is essential. Not only will it allow you to do your job properly, but it will also ensure your students fulfil their full potential.

Used literatures:

1. Flaherty, C. "How not to lose control of a class." Inside HigherEd; May 2015.

2. Knepp, K.A. “Understanding student and faculty incivility in higher education.” *Journal of Effective Teaching* 12, 2012.
3. McKeachie, W. J. and Svinicki, M. (2013) *McKeachie’s teaching tips : Strategies, research, and theory for college and university teachers*. (14th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
4. Utegenova, S. T. (2021). Audit quality control in Uzbekistan and all over the world. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 11(103), 328-332.
5. Turdi’muratovna, U. S., & Mukhiddin, U. (2022). Features of the process of transition from national accounting standards to international standards.
6. Bayjanov, S. X., & Utegenova, S. T. (2021). ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF AUDIT SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (8), 31-34.
7. Utegenova, S., Muratbaeva, A., & Xaliqnazarova, G. (2021). PRACTICAL STATUS OF EXTERNAL QUALITY CONTROL OF AUDITS: ON THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN AND FOREIGN COUNTRIES. *International journal of Business, Management and Accounting*, 1(1).
8. Bazarov, S. (2023). SO ‘G ‘D YOZUVI. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(15), 57-59.
9. Bazarov, S. (2023). Avesto yozuvi. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(13), 32-35.
10. Abdinazarovich, B. S. (2022). YOZUV VA UNING KELIB CHIQISH TARIXI. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(4), 116-119.
11. Serofiddin o'g, S. G. A. (2024). NEURAL CELLS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 3(30), 119-126.

12. Serofiddin o'g, S. G. A. (2024). MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF THE WASTE RECYCLING SYSTEM IN THE MODERN WORLD. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 5(42), 32-41.
13. Жамолова, Г. М. К., Хамрақулова, С. О. К., & Уралова, Н. Б. К. (2024). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НЕЙРОННЫХ СЕТЕЙ У ЧЕЛОВЕКА НА ПРИМЕРЕ РОБОТОТЕХНИКИ. *Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика)*, (6), 395-402.
14. Jamolova, G. (2023, May). PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA SINOV ISHLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA O 'TKAZISH METODIKASI. In *International Scientific and Practical Conference on Algorithms and Current Problems of Programming*.
15. Jamolova, G. M. (2022). PROFESSIONAL TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA O 'QUVCHILARGA INFORMATIKA FANINI O 'QITISHNING METODIK MODELI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(2), 102-109.
16. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.
17. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. *Interpretation and researches*, (4 (26)).
18. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So 'Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. *Scholar*, 1(13), 22-27.
19. Navruza, A. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *ITALY" ACTUAL*

PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"., 14(1).

20. Shodieva, G. (2023). TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 2(4), 40-46.
21. Yusupova, S. A. Z., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(1), 300-304.
22. Shodieva, G. (2023). ANALYSIS OF TRANSPOSITION OF WORD GROUPS. *Science and innovation*, 2(C9), 28-30.
23. Mirzayeva, D. I., & Shodiyeva, G. N. Q. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *Scientific progress*, 4(5), 94-98.